

**MUST THE STATE HAVE A RELIGIOUS FOUNDATION FOR
THERE TO BE A SUFFICIENT MORAL CONSENSUS IN SOCIETY?**

by
Prasanna Kumar Monditoka (M.Div. M.Pharm.)
Public Theologian

Abstract

God created humans as his image-bearers with the capabilities of reasoning and faculties to take moral decisions. He established a natural law and equipped his moral creatures with a conscience. A religious foundation is not necessary for the moral consensus in society. Christians should learn to live with a larger culture that does not have a religious foundation and strive to promote biblical values in that culture. A theonomy is evidently not an answer to the broken culture. The natural law provides the basis for Christians to seek the moral consensus from the rulers and culture. The scriptures suggest that a religious foundation is not necessary for a moral consensus in society and give principles for Christians to live faithfully in the world and remind the rulers and government of their duty to administer justice.

MUST THE STATE HAVE A RELIGIOUS FOUNDATION FOR THERE TO BE A SUFFICIENT MORAL CONSENSUS IN SOCIETY?

God created humans as his image-bearers with the capability of reasoning and faculties to take moral decisions and he established natural law and equipped his moral creatures with a conscience. Therefore, it is possible for humans to achieve sufficient moral consensus without a religious foundation. When we appeal for justice, equality, and human rights, we are appealing to the larger culture in spite of their religion and political stance. The basic assumption is that they are created in God's image, they have the faculties to reason, and they can perceive the natural law which is evident in creation.

First, a religious foundation is not essential for Christians to live peacefully and promote morality in the world. Christians should learn to live with a larger culture that does not have a religious foundation. Christians are minorities in most countries where there is no Christian foundation for politics. By the very definition, politics is the art of living together in the community.¹ John Stott defines politics as "the process whereby a group of people, whose opinions or interests are divergent, reach collective decisions which are binding on the whole group and enforced as common policy."² According to this definition, politics assumes a diversity of views on the goals for the community and methods to achieve those goals. We cannot expect consensus on every political issue when the community is composed of diverse value systems with religions and non-religions. However, Christians can still strive for justice, liberty, and equality for all people by persuasion, promotion, and persistence. Martin Luther King Jr. is a classic example of how to transform a culture by fighting against injustice. He led a non-violent civil rights movement and called for legal, economic, educational, and attitudinal

¹ Mark W. Charlton, *Christian Worldview and the Academic Disciplines: Crossing the Academy*, ed. Downey, Deane E.D, and Stanley E Porter (Eugene: Pickwick Publications, 2009), 405.

² Charlton, 405-406.

change. He championed civil rights for African Americans, and he strove for the forgiveness and reconciliation of Black and white races.³

Second, a theonomy is not an answer to the broken culture.⁴ Although many Christians desire to seek out a theonomy for achieving moral consensus, it is not achievable and also does not guarantee a biblical model for government. Theonomy is a hypothetical government form in which the Mosaic covenant is applied to the current political government. The problem with theonomy is that it is not based on careful biblical exegesis. It confuses the boundaries between church and state and degenerates religious distinctiveness. Although it correctly understands and applies the moral force of Mosaic civil law, it fails to understand the discontinuity of the old covenant and the inauguration of the new covenant with the hope of an already and not yet kingdom. It seeks glory in the present age. Theonomy undermines God's eternal law revealed in natural law. The Christendom in medieval Europe did not yield a just society; on the other hand, it brought disrepute on Christianity for the moral failures of church and state. At last, the Bible did not endorse a theonomy in the state; rather, it mandates Christians to be subjected to their political government and pray for the rulers in that government.⁵

Third, natural law provides the basis for Christians to seek moral consensus from the rulers and culture.⁶ Natural law is a moral theory that affirms that God gave a universal moral order in creation that governs our reasoning and behavior. Andrew Walker pointed out that natural law implies that humans are capable of comprehending which actions are good and eminently reasonable without appealing to God's word. Natural law provides the basis for morality for all people. Walker argued that politicians can govern justly without committing the state to a formal religious or philosophical obligation. Henry underscored that the role of government is not to judge between philosophical systems and establish one among others. According to him, the government's role is to ensure and secure a free course for everyone. It does not lead to moral neutrality; rather, it allows the government to not rely on one religious or nonreligious system.⁷

At last, scriptures suggest that a religious foundation is not necessary for a moral consensus in society. In Romans 2:14-15, Paul explained that gentiles are capable of distinguishing good from evil without the knowledge of God's word, and they show that the law is written in their hearts. This law is nothing but God's natural law given to humanity. In Romans

³ Craig A Carter, *Rethinking Christ and Culture: A Post-Christendom Perspective* (Grand Rapids: Brazos Press, 2006), 190.

⁴ Andrew T. Walker, "American Culture Is Broken. Is Theonomy the Answer?" *The Gospel Coalition*, March 2021, <https://www.thegospelcoalition.org/article/theonomy/>.

⁵ Andrew T. Walker, "American Culture Is Broken. Is Theonomy the Answer?" *The Gospel Coalition*, March 2021, <https://www.thegospelcoalition.org/article/theonomy/>.

⁶ Andrew T. Walker, *Liberty for All: Defending Everyone's Religious Freedom in a Pluralistic Age* (United States: Baker Publishing Group, 2021), 36.

⁷ Andrew T. Walker, *Liberty for All*, 37-38.

13:1-7, Paul admonished that Christians should subject themselves to governing authorities, and he emphasized that all authorities and human governments are instituted by the sovereign plan of God. He underscored that if someone is resisting the authorities, in a sense, they are resisting God. This admonition implies that human governments and rulers are equipped with moral knowledge through natural law. There was no appeal given to Christians to fight for religious conversions of the rulers or seek a religious government. In Matthew 22:17-22, Jesus clarifies that we are expected to give taxes to rulers, as it belongs to them, and we are expected to serve God, as we belong to him as image-bearers. Religious affairs are distinct from civil and political affairs.⁸

As we are arguing for natural law, we understand the fallenness of humanity, bondage, and blindness caused by sin and the Prince of Darkness. Christians should not be surprised when they see injustice, inequality, and unnatural rules in society in spite of the natural. The larger culture, influenced by the power of the evil one and darkness, does not respect God's moral law revealed in nature. When the state fails to rule justly or acts unjustly, Christians should remind and persuade the governing authorities, rulers, and society to act justly for moral good. Christians should live as light in the fallen world and strive to permeate the world with God's standards and his moral law in the world.

Conclusion

A religious foundation is not necessary for the moral consensus in society, as God imbedded natural law in his creation to distinguish what is good for human flourishing. First, Christians should learn to live with a larger culture that does not have a religious foundation and strive to promote biblical values in that culture. Second, a theonomy is evidently not an answer to the broken culture. Third, natural law provides the basis for Christians to seek the moral consensus from the rulers and culture. At last, scriptures suggest that a religious foundation is not necessary for a moral consensus in society and give principles for Christians to live faithfully in the world and remind the rulers and government of their duty to administer justice.

⁸ Andrew T, Walker, *Liberty for All*, 38-41.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Carter, Craig A. *Rethinking Christ and Culture: A Post-Christendom Perspective*. Grand Rapids: Brazos Press, 2006.

Charlton, Mark W. *Christian Worldview and the Academic Disciplines: Crossing the Academy*. Edited by Downey, Deane E.D, and Stanley E Porter. Eugene: Pickwick Publications, 2009.

Walker, Andrew T. “American Culture Is Broken. Is Theonomy the Answer?” *The Gospel Coalition*, March 2021. <https://www.thegospelcoalition.org/article/theonomy/>.

Walker, Andrew T. *Liberty for All: Defending Everyone's Religious Freedom in a Pluralistic Age*. United States: Baker Publishing Group, 2021.